

THE ROLE OF THE STATE COMMISSION FOR THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION AGAINST “CORRUPTION AS PUBLIC VALUE” IN THE POLITICAL SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

According to the European Commission’s 2024 Report on North Macedonia, Chapter 23: Judiciary and Fundamental Rights includes a section on the fight against corruption which states: “North Macedonia is between having some level of preparation and a moderate level of preparation and has made no progress in the prevention and fight against corruption. Corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern. The current government has stated that the fight against corruption is a priority”. Following a series of tragic events in which North Macedonia lost a large number of young lives, the slogan “Corruption kills” emerged in public discourse. Every public and private institution within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia should develop anti-corruption policies and mechanisms; however, the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (hereinafter: SCPC, the Commission) is one of the cores public institutions tasked with establishing an efficient system for the prevention and repression of corruption and conflict of interest.

This paper analyzes the annual reports of the SCPC from 2004-2024, focusing on submissions concerning the work of state bodies and local self-government units, as well as the Commission’s role in supporting the implementations of anti-corruption measures and policies. The central research question is: Is the SCPC effective and efficient in addressing “corruption as a public value” in the Republic of North Macedonia?

Keywords: *corruption, political system, anti-corruptive, policies, effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a global issue and one of the most serious problems within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia. Corruption is defined as the abuse of function, public authority, official duty, or position for the purpose of gaining benefit, either directly or through an intermediary, for oneself or for another (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019).

According to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption (2003), “corruption is an insidious plague that has a wide range of corrosive effects on societies. It undermines democracy and the rule of law, leads to violations of human rights, distorts markets, erodes the quality of life and allows organized crime, terrorism and other threats

to human security to flourish...Corruption is no longer a local matter but a transnational phenomenon that affects all societies and economies, making international cooperation to prevent and control it essential.”

Corruption is manifested through nepotism, bribery, cronyism, clientelism, party control over institutions, and other forms. A social public value is one that provides a normative consensus regarding the rights, benefits, and prerogatives to which citizens are entitled; the civic duties of individuals toward society and the state; and the principles upon which authority and public policies should be based (Bozeman, 2007).

If corruption is a phenomenon that violates norms directed toward the public good in order to obtain benefits for individuals or organized groups, then the phenomenon of “corruption as a public value” represents the acceptance of corruption as a norm. It becomes justified and culturally embedded within the political system – that is, corruption becomes part of the culture of governance (management). In this context, corruption is not perceived as an exception but as a normal mode of operation, which significantly complicates efforts to suppress it. “Corruption as a public value” is characterized by strong public condemnation, coupled with low awareness of personal participation in corrupt activities and insufficient reaction from citizens as well as public and state institutions.

A political system is a set of different formal legal institutions that constitute a government. In other words, it is the system of government in a nation (Hill, 2022). In democratic political systems, every state and public institution is part of the political system and operates independently within the competences for which it exists. Decentralization is among the most significant reforms of the past 50 years and it refers to the transfer of powers, responsibilities, and resources from the central government to elected authorities at the subnational level with a certain degree of authority (OECD, 2019). What must be emphasized is the decentralization of power among institution within the political system, meaning that the political system should not be equated with a political party system.

As noted in the European Commission Report (2024): “North Macedonia is between having some level of preparation and a moderate level of preparation and has made no progress in the prevention and fight against corruption. Corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern. The current government has stated that the fight against corruption is a priority.”

In 2023, several social and societal problems were intertwined among the top five concerns of citizens. Alongside corruption, political instability, poverty, crime and low income were identified as the most serious issues. Notably, healthcare protection has been gradually rising among citizen’s concerns. As in previous years, ethnic issues and environmental pollution ranked lowest. If organized crime and corruption are correlated and require similar measures for suppression, it can be concluded that the fight against corruption and organized crime remains among the most pressing social issued for citizens.” (Macedonian Center for International Cooperation, 2023).

In 2024, the Republic of North Macedonia ranked 88th on Transparency International’s Corruption Perceptions Index, scoring two points lower than the previous year and dropping twelve places overall.

The State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) is an independent institution within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia. It was established in 2002 under the Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Закон за спречување на корупцијата, 2002), began operating in 2003, and acquired the status of a legal entity – an independent state body – in 2004.

The SCPC was created to lead the fight against corruption by implementing anti-corruption policies, conducting inspections, issuing opinions and recommendations, initiating procedures related to conflicts of interest and illicit enrichment, and demanding institutional accountability – thereby distinguishing political responsibility from criminal liability. The SCPC should be recognized as non-selective, objective, and transparent in its operations within the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia.

2. THE ROLE OF THE SCPC IN THE POLITICAL SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

The establishment of the SCPC stemmed from the Criminal Law Convention on Corruption of the Council of Europe from 1999 (ratified by the Republic of Macedonia in 2002), which recommends that member states, in their measures and activities to combat corruption, establish specialized and independent anti-corruption bodies.

This obligation is also consistent with the United Nations Convention Against Corruption of 2003, ratified by the Republic of Macedonia in 2007, according to which the country, as a member of the global organization, committed itself to providing the specialized anti-corruption body with the conditions for autonomous and independent work, contributing to its material stability and capacity-building for effective and professional performance of its functions, as well as protecting it from any form of influence or pressure.

The SCPC is responsible for implementing the Law on Prevention of Corruption and the Law on Prevention of Conflict of Interest. It is also authorized to oversee lobbying activities in accordance with the Law on Lobbying. With the amendments to the Law on Prevention of Corruption that came into force in November 2010, unlike in the previous period, the position of member of the State Commission is exercised professionally.

The goal of the SCPC is to work toward preventing corruption and conflicts of interest in all spheres of government and public authority, promoting legal certainty and good governance, and encouraging a culture of integrity and accountability. According to Luis de Sousa “Anti-corruption agencies (ACAs) are public (funded) bodies of a durable nature, with a specific mission to fight corruption and reduce the opportunity structures conducive to its occurrence in society through preventive and/or repressive measures” (Ilik, 2023).

In 2003, the State Program for the Prevention and Repression of Corruption was prepared and adopted as a national project, and in 2005 an Annex to the State Program for the Prevention and Repression of Corruption was also adopted. These documents preceded the National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (2020–2024; 2021–2025), which represents a comprehensive document providing the main guidelines for the reform plan aimed at combating corruption.

The main legal acts that regulate the work of the SCPC are: the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia; the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest; the Electoral Code; the Law on Financing of Political Parties; the Criminal Code; the Law on Public Procurement; the Law on Lobbying; the Law on Whistleblower Protection, and the Law on Free Access to Public Information (JKCK, 2024).

3. ANALYSIS OF THE ANNUAL REPORTS OF THE SCPC

According to Article 19 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, “The State Commission shall submit an annual report on its work to the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia no later than March 31 of the current year, covering the previous year. The annual report of the State Commission is also submitted to the President

of the Republic of Macedonia, the Government of the Republic of Macedonia, and the media.”

The SCPC’s annual report contains statistical data on initiated cases, resolved cases, and cases under processing in accordance with its competencies, including analysis; the number of initiatives submitted to the public prosecutor’s office and other authorities; information on institutions that have not complied with the Commission’s requests; the number of cases for which misdemeanor proceedings have been initiated; an assessment of the implementation of this law; and an evaluation of the state of corruption and anti-corruption efforts in the country. At the request of the Assembly of the Republic of Macedonia, the SCPC is also obliged to submit a report covering a period shorter than one year” (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019).

An analysis of the SCPC’s annual reports shows that from 2004 to 2024, annual reports on its activities were regularly prepared, except for 2017 and 2018. Since the purpose of this study is to analyze all annual reports, information was requested from the SCPC regarding the missing reports for 2017 and 2018. The SCPC responded as follows:

- 2017 report: “The annual report on the SCPC’s work for the prevention of corruption for 2017 was not adopted by the SCPC because the members of the then Commission submitted their resignations.”
- 2018 report: “There is no annual report for 2018 because the new SCPC was elected with the adoption of the new Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest at the beginning of 2019.”

The SCPC’s response confirms that after the resignations of five out of seven members, the Commission did not have a quorum to operate and make decisions. The new composition of the SCPC was elected on February 8, 2019.

3.1 Where is corruption most prevalent?

In the annual reports from 2004 to 2024, the SCPC, through case processing, also analyzes the areas in which corruption is most prevalent and where state and public institutions do not exercise their authority efficiently. In the annual reports from 2004 to 2010, the majority of complaints within the SCPC’s competence concerned irregularities in the operations of state bodies, and after 2005, also in local government units. During this period, a special section of the annual reports addressed complaints involving corruption in public enterprises, healthcare, and education. In this way, state and public institutions that are part of the political system of the Republic of North Macedonia, and which manage public and state resources that can be misused through corrupt actions, are covered.

In 2010, the categorization of areas in which the SCPC operates changed, and specific figures for cases related to corruption in state bodies and local government units were no longer provided. Cases resolved in 2010 were divided into the following areas: prevention of corruption in politics, prevention of corruption in the exercise of public authority, prevention of corruption in carrying out matters of public interest, with the remaining cases categorized under judiciary and other areas. The 2010 report clearly states: “The SCPC’s work to date has shown that the warnings and recommendations it provides regarding the functioning of structures at both levels of government, central and local, are aimed at strengthening the national integrity system” (ДКСК, 2010).

Corruption in politics is mentioned in the 2005 report, which addresses corruption in the financing of political parties and corruption during electoral processes. “During the reporting period, the problem of political influence in elections, appointments, and dismissals of managerial positions remains relevant”. Here, the issue is not simply political

influence in general, but specifically the influence of political parties over public positions, which are fully partisan. This reflects apolitical behavior, completely contrary to the idea of politics as the organization of public matters through integrity, a system of merit, and accountability. In the 2006 annual report, terms such as “politics” and “political parties” are used. However, political parties are not synonymous with politics. The political system includes all state and public institutions, enterprises, and bodies, together with media, civil society organizations, interest groups, and individual citizens. Public policy refers to any decision at the local and central level that organize specific segment of citizens’ lives. Therefore, the narrative in the reports – particularly the sections addressing corruption in politics – is not entirely precise. A more accurate framing would be corruption within political parties and corruption during electoral processes.

In 2011, employment during the electoral period was effectively restricted, as the Employment Agency of the Republic of Macedonia could not process new job applications without prior approval from the SCPC. In the 2020 annual report, it is noted that the SCPC developed an application allowing the classification of reports by areas – executive power, judiciary, education, healthcare, urban planning and local government – as well as by types of problems, such as public procurement, employment, inspection oversight, issuance of permits, decisions, licenses, approvals and court rulings, in order to identify areas with the highest corruption risk (ДКСК, 2020).

The majority of reported illegalities were in the judiciary, executive branch, and local government units. In the 2021 and 2022 annual reports, analyses of corruption risk highlighted employment and urban planning as key areas. In 2023, the analysis focused on the judiciary sector. In 2024, anti-corruption oversight during the electoral period contributed to the opening of cases related to the misuse of public resources and public functions.

3.2 Anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation

The SCPC’s anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation is regulated by Article 17, paragraph 2 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (Закон за спречување на корупцијата и судирот на интереси, 2019), which grants the SCPC the authority to conduct anti-corruption reviews of laws and other regulations, preparing reports and opinions in the process. “The anti-corruption review of legislation is one of the preventive competencies of the State Commission and serves as a tool for identifying regulatory risks and addressing vulnerabilities in legal provisions that could enable corrupt practices” (ДКСК, 2024). This authority is directly linked to the anti-corruption review of public policies.

At the global level, anti-corruption legislative review was first conducted in Moldova in 2001, followed by Lithuania in 2002. “Anti-corruption assessment of legislation is a review of the form and substance of drafted or enacted legal rules in order to detect and minimize the risk of future corruption that the rules could facilitate” (Regional Cooperation Council, 2014).

According to Article 24, paragraph 1, item 7 of the Rules of Procedure of the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, Ministries and other authorized proposers must submit the materials they provide to the Government for review, adoption, confirmation, or enactment in advance for the opinion of the competent state administration bodies and other state authorities, depending on the nature of the material under consideration, and obligatorily to the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption – for draft laws subject to regulatory impact assessment, in order to carry out an anti-

corruption review (Деловник за работа на Владата на Република Северна Македонија, 2024).

According to the SCPC's annual reports, by 2015 an anti-corruption review had been conducted on a total of 63 legislative acts. However, in the annual reports for 2009, 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015, not a single anti-corruption review of legislation is recorded (ДКСК, 2010, 2013, 2015, 2016). In September 2015, the first Methodology for Anti-Corruption Review of Legislation was prepared and adopted. This methodology defined: the process of anti-corruption legislative review and the results of its implementation; the organization and management of the process; the role and responsibilities of each participant; and the involvement of stakeholders in the process.

If we compare the number of laws adopted by the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, based on the annual report on the implementation of the regulatory impact assessment process for the period from January to December 2022 (Министерство за информатичко општество и администрација, 2023), with the number of legislative acts that underwent anti-corruption review according to the SCPC's annual reports for the period 2014–2022, the following can be observed: In the SCPC's 2014 annual report, no anti-corruption review was conducted on any draft law, while 335 draft laws were adopted by the Government of the Republic of Macedonia that same year. In 2015, when again not a single anti-corruption review was conducted, 566 laws were adopted. In 2016, there is information that an anti-corruption review was conducted on only one legislative act, while a total of 252 draft laws were adopted. In 2017 and 2018, a total of 163 draft laws were adopted, but there are no SCPC annual reports for these years. In 2019, anti-corruption review was carried out on 8 draft laws, while 242 were adopted. In 2020, 121 draft laws were adopted, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 5 draft laws and 2 subsidiary acts. In 2021, when the SCPC developed a software solution intended to facilitate and accelerate the anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary acts, 12 laws and 5 subsidiary acts were reviewed, while 111 draft laws were adopted. In 2022, 68 laws were adopted, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 12 legislative acts, 4 draft laws, and 1 international treaty. Additionally, under the IPA project, analyses of discretionary powers were prepared for 7 legislative acts covering various areas of employment.

According to the monthly reviews of open draft laws on the Unique National Electronic Register of Regulations of the Republic of North Macedonia (Граѓански ресурсен центар, 2023, 2024), in 2023 a total of 71 draft laws were adopted at sessions of the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, while anti-corruption review was conducted on 13 existing legislative acts and 1 draft law published on ENER. Regarding detected legislative weaknesses and gaps in procedures for the appointment and dismissal of directors, acting officials, and temporary employees in public institutions, the SCPC carried out anti-corruption review of 4 legislative acts and 5 draft and proposed laws. In 2024, the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia adopted a total of 101 draft laws, and anti-corruption review was conducted on 21 legislative acts and subsidiary legislation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the SCPC's annual reports, it is not possible to definitively determine its effectiveness in addressing "corruption as a public value." The SCPC's annual reports indicate that corruption is most visible in the misuse of public and state resources managed by public and state institutions.

Following the development of the application in 2020 for categorizing corruption reports by sector and by type of problem, it has been confirmed that the judiciary, executive branch, local government units, employment, and urban planning remain the areas with the highest risk of corruption. Under the influence of the SCPC, in 2011 the space for new employment during the electoral period was effectively closed without prior approval from the SCPC. This represents a significant step forward in the area of public sector employment, where corruption is highly prevalent.

The anti-corruption review of laws and subsidiary legislation is one of the SCPC's most important competencies, aimed at preventing and identifying opportunities for corruption arising from the content of laws and subsidiary acts (public policies). The key challenge in exercising this authority stems from the failure of state institutions to fulfill their obligations to submit draft laws and subsidiary acts to the SCPC for anti-corruption review.

Despite significant progress in legislative regulations for combating corruption and conflicts of interest, and the professional execution of the SCPC's competencies, the 2023 SCPC annual report clearly emphasizes that "...this has not reduced the misuse of legislative acts due to imprecise or unclear provisions, so influences based on party, family, or friendship connections continue to dominate in the area of public sector employment. The abuse of functions and discretionary powers in issuing various permits, approvals, and contracts, as well as creating conditions for favoring certain companies, remains prevalent. Unlawful construction on state and private land, enabled by provisions in laws related to urban planning, construction, and the environment, combined with inaction by inspection services and their clientelism toward centers of political power and business elites, leaves citizens with little opportunity – even in courts – to defend their constitutionally guaranteed rights to equal employment opportunities, property protection, and a clean environment" (ДКСК, 2023).

Although the SCPC openly highlights systemic corrupt practices, its recommendations are often ignored or minimized. The SCPC strives to operate in an environment of institutional resistance within a political system where the political will to combat corruption is more declarative than real. The SCPC has a role in creating a new political and ethical narrative: that integrity is possible; the misuse of public goods, public functions, and public authority must not be overlooked; and that state and public institutions can exist outside partisan control.

The effectiveness of the SCPC depends on the implementation of its recommendations by other competent institutions within the political system that hold executive power, since the SCPC itself does not have executive authority and relies on institutional cooperation. Weak institutional capacity within public and state institutions results in underdeveloped inter-institutional collaboration across the political system, which directly affects the cooperation with the SCPC and, consequently, the implementation of its recommendations.

If institutions continue to disregard the SCPC's recommendations, corruption will remain entrenched in practice, inevitably resulting in a decline in public trust in state and public institutions and the strengthening of "corruption as a public value".

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